

STUDIES IN DEHYDROGENATION. PART V.

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The syntheses and selenium dehydrogenation of tetrahydrophenanthrene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclopentane and 9-methyltetrahydrophenanthrene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclopentane have been described. The former on dehydrogenation gives chrysene and the latter forms 3-methyl-1 : 2-benzanthracene.

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 349) an explanation of the mechanism of ring transformation of cyclopentane-spiro-hydrocarbons, during selenium dehydrogenation, had been offered. The results now obtained by the dehydrogenation of tetrahydrophenanthrene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclopentane (V, R=H) and 9-methyltetrahydrophenanthrene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclopentane (V, R=Me) go to support the former view.

The spiro-hydrocarbon (V, R=H) has been synthesised readily by the following steps. The anhydride of cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid condenses with naphthalene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride giving a mixture of two isomeric keto-acids. They are separated by fractional crystallisation and purified through the methyl ester. The lower melting keto-acid gives α -naphthoic acid on oxidation with sodium hypobromite and, therefore, it is $\alpha\alpha$ -cyclopentane- β -1-naphthoylpropionic acid (I, R=H),

whereas β -naphthoic acid is obtained from the less fusible one, which is, therefore, the β -2-naphthoyl acid (II). The position of the *cyclopentane* ring has been assumed from an analogy with the constitution of the keto-acids obtained by the condensation of the anhydride of *cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* with benzene and its homologues (*loc. cit.* p. 350). The keto-acid (I, R=H) on reduction by the Clemmensen method gives α -*cyclopentane- γ -1-naphthylbutyric acid* (III, R=H), which is cyclised with 85% sulphuric acid to 1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrophenanthrene-2:2-spiro-*cyclopentane* (IV, R=H). This spiro-keto compound on reduction by the Clemmensen method yields the spiro-hydrocarbon, 1:2:3:4-tetrahydrophenanthrene-2:2-spiro-*cyclopentane* (V, R=H). The latter on selenium dehydrogenation

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

gives only chrysene. It is quite likely that traces of 1:2-benzanthracene (VI, R=H) that might have been formed had escaped detection.

In a similar manner the spiro-hydrocarbon (V, R=Me) has also been synthesised. The anhydride of *cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* condenses with α -methyl-naphthalene, forming only one keto-acid. The keto-acid on oxidation with sodium hypochlorite gives 4-methyl-1-naphthoic acid and hence it is α -*cyclopentane- β -(4-methyl)-1-naphthoylpropionic acid* (I, R=Me). As noted before (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1939, 152, 11), due to the presence of a methyl group in *para*-position to the keto group, the reduction of the keto-acid (I, R=Me) to α -*cyclopentane- γ -(4-methyl)-1-naphthylbutyric acid* (III, R=Me) could only be accomplished when the low melting methyl ester of the keto-acid was used for reduction. On cyclisation with 85% sulphuric acid the naphthylbutyric acid (III, R=Me) gives 1-keto-9-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrophenanthrene-2:2-spiro-*cyclopentane* (IV, R=Me). This spiro-ketone on reduction by the Clemmensen method gives 9-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrophenanthrene-2:2-spiro-*cyclopentane* (V, R=Me). Curiously enough the ring transformation during the dehydrogenation of this spiro-hydrocarbon leads to the preferential formation of the linear anthracene

derivative, 3-methyl-1 : 2-benzanthracene (VI, R=Me) instead of the angular chrysene derivative.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

αα-cyclopentane-β-1 and αα-cyclopentane-β-2-naphthoylethylpropionic Acids (I, R=H and II).—A mixture of the anhydride of cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (31 g.) and naphthalene (40 g.) was slowly added to an ice-cooled solution of aluminium chloride (52 g.) in nitrobenzene (150 c.c.). The mixture was kept in the ice-bath for 4 hours and then at the room temperature for 12 hours. The product was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and nitrobenzene and excess of naphthalene were distilled off in steam. The solid product was extracted with sodium carbonate solution, from which the mixture of keto-acids separated on acidification. This was thoroughly washed with hot water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. The first crop recrystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless needles, m.p. 190-91°, yield 2.1 g. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 6.4. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 76.6; H, 6.4 per cent). The acetic acid mother-liquor was diluted with three times its own volume of hot water, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. The keto-acid, that separated out on cooling, was repeatedly crystallised from spirit, m.p. 135-40°. This impure acid was converted into the methyl ester by methyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride. The solid methyl ester after repeated crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. 50-60°) gave the pure substance, m.p. 69-70°, yield 5.5 g. (Found: C, 77.0; H, 6.7. $C_{19}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 77.0; H, 6.8 per cent). The lower melting keto-acid was obtained in a pure condition by the hydrolysis of the methyl ester and was crystallised from rectified spirit in fine needles, m.p. 140-41°. (Found: C, 76.58; H, 6.35. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 76.6; H, 6.4 per cent).

The methyl ester of the higher melting keto-acid, prepared by methyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride, crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 90-100°) in prismatic needles, m.p. 109-10°. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 6.9. $C_{19}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 77.0; H, 6.8 per cent).

Oxidation of the Keto-acid (m.p. 190-91°) *with Sodium Hypobromite Solution*.—The keto-acid (0.5 g.) was dissolved in 10% caustic soda solution and treated with sodium hypobromite solution (1.5 c.c. of bromine and 150 c.c. of 10% caustic soda solution) first in the cold and then warming on the water-bath for 1 hour. The solution was filtered and acidified with sulphurous and sulphuric acids. The separated solid was crystallised from spirit in needles, m.p. 182° (mixed m.p. with β-naphthoic acid).

The oxidation of the keto-acid (m.p. 140-41°) was carried out in a similar manner and the naphthoic acid, so obtained, after crystallisation from spirit melted at 160° (mixed m.p. with α -naphthoic acid).

aa-cyclopentane- γ -1-naphthylbutyric Acid (III, R=H).—*aa-cyclopentane- β -1-naphthoylpropionic acid* (6 g.) was gently boiled with amalgamated zinc (30 g.) and hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, ether removed and the residue purified by extraction with sodium carbonate solution and precipitation with hydrochloric acid. The pasty mass, thus obtained, distilled above 200° under high vacuum as a thick liquid. The distillate on cooling and stirring with petroleum ether (b.p. 50-60°) readily solidified. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 50-60°) in needles, m.p. 108-9°. (Found : C, 80·4 ; H, 7·5. $C_{18}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 80·61 ; H, 7·46 per cent).

1-Keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrophenanthrene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (IV, R=H).—*aa-cyclopentane- γ -1-naphthylbutyric acid* (3.5 g.) was cyclised with concentrated sulphuric acid (10.5 c.c.) and water (3.5 c.c.) at 100°. The product was obtained as a thick light yellow oil, b.p. 215°/6 mm., yield 2.4 g. (Found : C, 86·2 ; H, 7·3. $C_{18}H_{18}O$ requires C, 86·4 ; H, 7·2 per cent).

1:2:3:4-Tetrahydrophenanthrene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (V, R=H).—The foregoing spiro-ketone (2.5 g.) was heated with amalgamated zinc (15 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.) for 24 hours. The product was obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. 190-95°/8 mm., yield 2 g. (Found : C, 91·2 ; H, 8·6. $C_{18}H_{20}$ requires C, 91·5 ; H, 8·5 per cent).

Selenium Dehydrogenation of 1:2:3:4-Tetrahydrophenanthrene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane.—The spiro-hydrocarbon (1.8 g.) was heated with selenium (3.5 g.) in a metal-bath at 300-20° for 12 hours and at 340-50° for 24 hours. The product was extracted with chloroform and after removal of the solvent the residue was distilled over sodium under reduced pressure, when the distillate was obtained as a white solid. This was crystallised from hot benzene in shining flakes, m.p. 249° (mixed m.p. with chrysene). (Found : C, 94·6 ; H, 5·3. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{12}$: C, 94·75 ; H, 5·25 per cent).

aa-cyclopentane-(β -4-methyl)-1-naphthoylpropionic Acid (I, R=Me).—It was prepared as in the case of *aa-cyclopentane- β -1-naphthoylpropionic acid*, from the anhydride of *cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* (31 g.), α -methyl-naphthalene (30 g.) and aluminium chloride (54 g.), in nitrobenzene (150 c.c.) solution. The product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) and finally from alcohol, in which it is sparingly soluble, in colourless octahedra, m.p. 176-77°. (Found : C, 77·0 ; H, 6·9. $C_{19}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 77·0 ; H, 6·8 per cent).

The *methyl ester*, prepared by the action of methyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride, was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 50-60°) in cubes, m.p. 56-57°, yield 24 g. (Found : C, 77.2 ; H, 7.2. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 77.4 ; H, 7.1 per cent).

Oxidation of the Keto-acid (I, R=Me) with Sodium Hypochlorite Solution.—The keto-acid (1.2 g.) was boiled with sodium hypochlorite solution (from 100 c.c. of 10% caustic soda solution and chlorine from 2.1 g. of potassium permanganate and 15 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid), and the solution was cooled, filtered and acidified with sulphurous acid and sulphuric acids. The product was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 175-76°, which gave no depression with 4-methyl-1-naphthoic acid, prepared by Mayer and Sieglitz's method (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 1839).

α-cyclopentane-γ-(4-methyl)-1-naphthylbutyric Acid (III, R=Me).—The methyl ester of the foregoing keto-acid (I, R=Me) was gently boiled for 24 hours with amalgamated zinc (100 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.). The product was extracted with ether, the solvent removed and the residue distilled as a thick oil (13 g.) at 230-35°/5 mm. This was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash when 11.5 g. of the reduced acid was obtained. It crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 70-80°), m.p. 112°. (Found : C, 81.1 ; H, 7.7. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 80.9 ; H, 7.8 per cent).

9-Methyl-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrophenanthrene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (IV, R=Me).—The foregoing butyric acid (5 g.) was cyclised by heating on the steam-bath with concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) and water (5 c.c.) for 1½ hours. The solid product was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in granules, m.p. 97°. (Found: C, 86.2; H, 7.7. $C_{18}H_{20}O$ requires C, 86.4 ; H, 7.6 per cent).

9-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrophenanthrene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (V, R=Me).—The spiro-ketone (IV, R=Me) (3.5 g.), amalgamated zinc (20 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) were allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature overnight and then gently boiled for 24 hours. The solid product was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in long needles, m.p. 69-70°. (Found : C, 91.1 ; H, 8.8. $C_{18}H_{22}$ requires C, 91.2 ; H, 8.8 per cent).

Selenium Dehydrogenation of 9-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrophenanthrene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane.—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2.3 g.) was heated with 3 g. of selenium in a metal-bath at 280-320° for 8 hours and at 340-50° for 24 hours. The product was extracted with chloroform, the solvent evaporated and the residue was distilled over sodium. The distillate was collected at 240-50°/6 mm., as a thick oil which slowly solidified. The product was crystallised from benzene-petroleum (b.p. 50-60°) mixture in

clusters of short needles, m.p. 152-53°. The mixed m.p. with a sample of 3-methyl-1:2-benzanthracene prepared according to Cook (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1088) was 153°. (Found: C, 94.1; H, 5.8. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{14}$: C, 94.2; H, 5.8 per cent).

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